

MAPWORMS

Mimicking Adaptation
and Plasticity in
WORMS

D3.3 MORPHING OF STRUCTURES: INVERSE IBV PROBLEM

Deliverable Number	D3.3
Work package Number and Title	WP3 – Annelid shape-morphing modelling
Lead Beneficiary	SSSA
Version – Status	Final
Due Date	April 30, 2025
Deliverable Type	R — Document, report
Dissemination Level	PU - Public
Internal Reviewer	Hasan Dad Ansari Mohammad Kleoniki Keklikoglou
Filename	MAPWORMS_D3.3_Morphing of structures: Inverse IBV problem_v1-2_20250430

Funded by
the European Union

European
Innovation
Council

This project has received funding from the European Union's
Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under
grant agreement N° 101046846

DOCUMENT INFO

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DOCUMENT HISTORY

Date	Version	Editor	Change	Status
28/04/2025	V1.1	Antonio DeSimone	First Draft	Draft
29/04/2025	V1.2	Hasan Dad Ansari Mohammad Kleoniki Keklikoglou	Internal Revisions	Draft
30/04/2025	V2.1	Antonio DeSimone	Final Version	Draft
30/04/2025	VF	Arianna Menciassi	Document Submission	Final

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1 INTRODUCTION

The MAPWORMS project proposes a novel robot concept which aims at replicating the shape-morphing abilities of simplified forms of marine worms (Figure 1). Within this framework, Sipuncula, a class of unsegmented marine Annelida worms, serve as the primary source of bioinspiration for designing the final robots, due to their straightforward yet effective morphological structure (Figure 1A). This structure enables impressive deformations of their shape and protrusion abilities of part of their bodies, including eversion of a specific structure (introvert). In the final robots, these abilities will be mimicked by combining synthetic soft actuation units into a smart and modular architecture capable of responding to various stimuli (Figure 1B).

Figure 1: (A) Body parts of Sipuncula worms which have been selected as main source of bioinspiration for the design of the final robots developed within the project. (B) Design concept of the worm-inspired robot that will be developed within the project. The final robots will feature a smart and modular architecture by combining actuation units capable of responding to different stimuli.

To be able to reproduce some of the behaviors of Sipuncula and similar marine worms, it is helpful to model them in a way that is simple enough to be translated into the design and optimization of an artificial device, that is, models that can cover the gap between biology and technology. To do this, building on what has been presented in Deliverable D2.2 “First set of parameters for modelling”, D3.1 “Validated morphing algorithm for smart hydrogels based on non-Euclidean plates”, and D3.2 “Morphing of structures-direct IBV problem”, we have continued our development of a 3D model based on the notion of multiplicative decomposition of the deformation gradient, that can be adopted to mimic worm behaviors by means of actively imposing a target 3D metric tensor. In particular, in this deliverable D3.3 we have focused on inverse design for morphing and locomotion problems, namely, how to program the target metric to achieve a desired shape without storing internal stresses, and how to program body contractions to achieve eversion and rectilinear

burrowing motion of a robotic worm mimicking the Sipuncula. These mechanisms are particularly useful as they can be easily adapted to different actuation strategies.

2 MORPHING BY MEANS OF AN INTRINSIC DEFORMATION

We begin with a quick review of the morphing problem, as discussed in previous deliverables. Materials can undergo spontaneous anelastic deformations that persist even without applied stress, such as during growth phenomena, gel swelling, thermal expansion and so on. A possible way to describe these phenomena is to postulate a “multiplicative decomposition” of the deformation gradient F . This method splits the deformation gradient

$$F = \nabla f$$

where f is the map transforming the reference configuration in the deformed one, into the product of two components:

$$F = F_e F_0,$$

where the tensor F_e describes the elastic component of the deformation (i.e., the part of the deformation responsible for the storing of internal elastic energy and build-up of internal stress, and that is recovered as F_e^{-1}) while F_0 describes an active component (which can be modulated thanks to biological activity, muscle contraction, thermal distortions, gel swelling, etc. and leads to residual deformations that persist even when the material is under no applied external stresses) [1,2,3,4].

The advantage in this representation is that we can impose a certain active deformation (in response to a stimulus when modelling actuation units made of smart materials like smart hydrogels, or in response to muscle contraction when modelling living organisms like worms) by means of prescribing an evolution law for F_0 . A typical format for F_a is the following transversally isotropic stretch:

$$(F_a)_{ij} = \lambda_{par} n_i n_j + \lambda_{perp} (\delta_{ij} - n_i n_j),$$

where δ_{ij} is the Kronecker symbol, the unit vector n describes a distinguished direction (e.g., the one of muscle fibers) and λ_{par} λ_{perp} are the stretches in the direction parallel and perpendicular to n , respectively.

We typically denote the strain in the direction of n as ϵ_a , and assume no change perpendicular to n :

$$\lambda_{par} = 1 + \epsilon_a,$$

$$\lambda_{perp} = 1$$

2.1 2D TARGET METRIC AND TARGET CURVATURE IN KOITER'S SHELL THEORY

In a first approximation, the introvert of Sipuncula can be regarded as an axisymmetric, pseudo-cylindrical structure. Since these structures are “thin”, i.e., their thickness is much smaller than their radius and length, we can adopt Koiter’s shell theory and express the areal density η_{elast} of their elastic energy as:

$$\eta_{elast} \propto t\|a - a_0\|^2 + t^3\|b - b_0\|^2,$$

where t is the initial thickness of the cylindrical structure, and a, b its first and second fundamental forms [5]. According to this formulation, in place of prescribing the entire deformation gradient F_a , we can control the shape of our structures by means of imposing intrinsic terms a_0, b_0 , which correspond to certain “target metric” and “target curvatures”. Additionally, for very thin structures ($t^3 \ll t$), the former expression can be simplified to:

$$\eta_{elastic} \propto t\|a - a_0\|^2,$$

so that it is enough to prescribe a target metric a_0 for the structure’s surface.

Elastic energy minimization will typically result in the surface achieving the target shape $a = a_0$. The curvature of the surface will then follow from the Theorema Egregium by Gauss that states that Gaussian curvature (the determinant of the second fundamental form b) is determined by the first fundamental form a . In the case of axisymmetric structures, this essentially means prescribing the stretches along coordinate curves (parallels and meridians) which have a direct counterpart in the muscular system of Sipuncula (circular and longitudinal muscles, see deliverable D2.4). Further details and examples of the application of the concept of target metric to morphing structures can be found in [6].

2.2 3D MORPHING OF INTROVERT-LIKE STRUCTURES

According to the same philosophy, in deliverable D3.2 “Morphing of structures-direct IBV problem”, we extended our scope from the axisymmetric 2D view of Deliverable D3.1 “Validated morphing algorithm for smart hydrogels based on non-Euclidean plates” to a fully 3D one, where the target metric of a surface (2D matrix) is replaced by a 3D target deformation tensor (\mathbf{F}_0) of the corresponding “thick surface”, that is, a thin sheet with a nonzero thickness.

To validate this framework, we considered an interesting example of eversion, reminiscent of the tentacular crown-protrusion mechanism used by Sipuncula in the very last part of their introvert. This is given by a cylinder that everts completely (that is, the initially internal surface becomes external and vice versa) passing through cones with higher and higher opening angle α (see Fig.3 in the Results section). To describe this, we employed the multiplicative decomposition of the deformation gradient, seen in the previous section, and imposed \mathbf{F}_0 to be equal to a desired target metric corresponding to more and more slanted cones ($\mathbf{F}_0 \triangleq \mathbf{F}_0(\alpha)$). Moreover, we assumed that the cylinder is made of an elastic material with an internal elastic energy described by

$$E(f; F_0) = \int_B \Psi(F_e) dV, \quad F_e = FF_0^{-1}$$

and developed a 3D FEM model on COMSOL Multiphysics (Solid Mechanics module), adopting a hyperelastic description with an elastic energy density ψ given by the St Venant-Kirchhoff expression. This energy density is always non-negative, and minimized at the value zero only by the identity matrix $\mathbf{F}_e = \mathbf{1}$.

We then considered a direct morphing problem: Given a field of active distortions \mathbf{F}_0 , find the deformation map \mathbf{f}^* minimizing the elastic energy \mathbf{E} , namely,

$$\mathbf{f}^*(\mathbf{F}_0) = \underset{\mathbf{f}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \int_B \psi(\mathbf{F}_e) dV, \quad \mathbf{F}_e = \nabla \mathbf{f} \mathbf{F}_0^{-1}$$

Depending on whether the active distortion field \mathbf{F}_0 is kinematically compatible or not, i.e., whether deformations \mathbf{f} such that $\nabla \mathbf{f} = \mathbf{F}_0$ exist or not, the energy and stresses associated with the minimizer \mathbf{f}^* may or may not vanish. In the first case, the structure can actually find a configuration with $\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}_0$, which implies $\mathbf{F}_e = \mathbf{1}$, and the internal elastic energy of the system is minimized at the lowest possible value, namely zero.

The fact that energy and stresses associated with the minimizer \mathbf{f}^* vanish guarantee that they are achievable as equilibrium configuration in the absence of external forces. For this reason, compatible active distortion fields are key to achieve programmable morphing. In deliverable D3.2, we considered an empirical procedure which works well for very thin structures. We prescribed the evolving geometry of the mid-surface, and then extruded the active deformation field in the thickness direction by simple empirical rules. While this procedure does not guarantee exact kinematic compatibility, it does ensure approximate kinematic compatibility due to the thinness of the domain in the direction perpendicular to the mid-surface. In fact, we could verify its effectiveness in the programmed eversion of a thin cylinder, as discussed below in Section 2.1.1 and Figure 3. In this deliverable D3.3, however, we tackle the problem of exact compatibility directly, through the formulation and solution of an inverse morphing problem. By this, we mean: given a sought shape \mathbf{f}^* , design an active distortion field \mathbf{F}_0 such that $\mathbf{f}^*(\mathbf{F}_0)$ is a stress-free configuration. This is further discussed in Section 3.

2.2.1 EVERSION OF THIN CYLINDERS

Let us consider a cylinder with mid radius R_0 , height H_0 , and thickness t_0 . Since it is an axisymmetric structure, we can describe it in terms of its cross-section in the r-z plane, where z is the axis of symmetry and r is the distance from that axis. Given a generic point $q = (r, z)$ on the cross-section, let us define as $d(q)$ its distance from the mid surface. In particular, in the initial cylindrical configuration we have:

$$d_0(q) = R_0 - r.$$

Let us then consider a deformation that maps the mid surface of the cylinder into a cone with aperture angle $\pi - 2\alpha$ (see Fig.3). The current radius R on the mid surface can be expressed as:

$$R = R_0 + z \cos(\alpha) = R_0(1 + \epsilon_a(R_0, z)), \quad \epsilon_a(R_0, z) = \frac{\cos(\alpha)}{R_0} z,$$

Where $\epsilon_a(r, z)$ is the strain in the direction of the parallels when considering a local cylindrical coordinate frame.

To find an expression for ϵ_a at the generic point q , we further require the deformation to leave the thickness of the cylinder unchanged, that is, we require the distance between any point and the mid surface to remain constant in the deformation process. Given q , we can express its current $d(q)$ as:

$$d(q) = \frac{\Delta r}{\sin(\alpha)}, \quad \Delta r = R - \rho,$$

Where ρ is the current radius of the point q . Therefore, substituting in the parallel strain, we can rewrite the previous expression as

$$\begin{aligned} d(q) &= \frac{R - \rho}{\sin(\alpha)} = \frac{1}{\sin(\alpha)} (R_0(1 + \epsilon_a(R_0, z)) - r(1 + \epsilon_a(r, z))) = \\ &= \frac{1}{\sin(\alpha)} (R_0 - r + R_0\epsilon_a(R_0, z) - r\epsilon_a(r, z)). \end{aligned}$$

Finally, the fact that thickness does not change gives us:

$$d_0(q) = R_0 - r = \frac{1}{\sin(\alpha)} (R_0 - r + R_0\epsilon_a(R_0, z) - r\epsilon_a(r, z)),$$

By substituting in the expression for $\epsilon_a(R_0, z)$ and rearranging we obtain:

$$\epsilon_a(r, z) = \left(\frac{R_0}{r} - 1 \right) (1 - \sin(\alpha)) + \frac{\cos(\alpha)}{r} z.$$

Using this expression in the target deformation tensor F_0 , we obtain a family of deformed and everted shapes, starting from the upright cylindrical one, shown in Figure 3.

3 INVERSE MORPHING BY MEANS OF AN EXACTLY COMPATIBLE ACTIVE DISTORTION

The existence of stress-free configurations generated by the prescription of a compatible distortion field is a subject of great importance in the field of programmed morphing. These configurations are special elastic solutions which minimize the elastic energy at zero stress, hence are admissible equilibrium configurations in the absence of external forces. We follow

[7,8] and introduce the (natural, or target) metric tensor field $C_0 = F_0^T F_0$ associated with the field of active distortion F_0 . A crucial notion to test for kinematic compatibility of a metric tensor field is the associated Riemann curvature. Its vanishing guarantees that the metric tensor is kinematically compatible, as explained below.

Given a metric tensor \mathbf{G} , its associated Riemann curvature $\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{G})$ is constructed from linear combinations of second derivatives of the components of \mathbf{G} ; the usual representation of $\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{G})$ is done in terms of the Christoffel symbols. For all $i, j, k, q \in \{1, 2, 3\}$, let the functions Γ_{ijq} and Γ_{ij}^p be the Christoffel symbols of the first and second kind, respectively, defined by

$$\Gamma_{ijq} = \frac{1}{2} (\partial_j \mathbf{G}_{ij} + \partial_i \mathbf{G}_{jq} + \partial_q \mathbf{G}_{ij}),$$

and

$$\Gamma_{ij}^p = \mathbf{G}^{pq} \Gamma_{ijq},$$

where $\mathbf{G}^{pq} = \mathbf{G}_{pq}^{-1}$. Then, the Riemann curvature tensor associated with \mathbf{C} is given by:

$$\mathbf{R}_{qijk} = \partial_j \Gamma_{ikq} - \partial_k \Gamma_{ijq} + \Gamma_{ij}^p \Gamma_{kqp} - \Gamma_{ik}^p \Gamma_{jqp}.$$

In a 3D space, the Riemann tensor has 81 components, but most of them are zero or redundant; actually, in 3D, \mathbf{R} can be represented at glance by a 3×3 skew-symmetric matrix, whose entries are 3×3 skew-symmetric matrices, see below. The skew symmetry implies that only six strict components remain. As this representation shows, the 3 matrices on the diagonal contain only zero entries; moreover, all the matrices out of diagonal are skew-symmetric, and have only zero entries on their diagonals:

$$\mathbf{R} = \begin{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \mathbf{R}_{1212} & \mathbf{R}_{1213} \\ \text{skw} & 0 & \mathbf{R}_{1223} \\ \text{skw} & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \mathbf{R}_{1312} & \mathbf{R}_{1313} \\ \text{skw} & 0 & \mathbf{R}_{1323} \\ \text{skw} & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \\ \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\mathbf{R}_{1212} & -\mathbf{R}_{1213} \\ 0 & 0 & -\mathbf{R}_{1223} \\ \text{skw} & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \mathbf{R}_{2312} & \mathbf{R}_{2313} \\ 0 & 0 & \mathbf{R}_{2323} \\ \text{skw} & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \\ \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\mathbf{R}_{1312} & -\mathbf{R}_{1313} \\ 0 & 0 & -\mathbf{R}_{1323} \\ \text{skw} & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\mathbf{R}_{2312} & -\mathbf{R}_{1323} \\ 0 & 0 & -\mathbf{R}_{2323} \\ \text{skw} & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Moreover, due to major symmetry, $\mathbf{R}_{1312} = \mathbf{R}_{1213}$, $\mathbf{R}_{2312} = \mathbf{R}_{1223}$, and $\mathbf{R}_{1323} = \mathbf{R}_{2313}$. Consequently, the equation $\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{C}) = \mathbf{0}$ consists of six partial differential equations involving the six strict components of \mathbf{C} ; this system of six PDEs might be used as a tool to characterize compatible fields \mathbf{F}_0 .

Given a smooth, positive definite, symmetric tensor field \mathbf{G} on a simple-connected domain \mathcal{B} , the necessary and sufficient condition for \mathbf{G} to be the metric tensor of a realizable configuration is that its associated Riemann curvature tensor $\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{G})$ vanish; we have:

$$\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{G}) = 0 \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad \exists f \text{ s.t. } \nabla f^T \nabla f = \mathbf{G}.$$

Moreover, the embedding f is *unique* up to a global isometry, and \mathbf{G} is called an Euclidean metric tensor. The same test can be done on the natural metric \mathbf{C}_o to assess its compatibility of \mathbf{F}_o , that is

$$\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{C}_o) = 0 \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad \exists f \text{ s.t. } \nabla f^T \nabla f = \mathbf{C}_o,$$

and the natural metric \mathbf{C}_o is Euclidean; the configuration $f(\mathcal{B})$ is then realizable, stress-free, and unique up to isometries.

3.1 EVERSION OF THICK CYLINDERS

While the procedure described in Section 2.2.1 gives good results only on sufficiently thin cylinders, the one described in this section gives exact results on cylinders of arbitrary thickness. Examples of everted shapes on thick cylinders obtained by prescribing active distortion fields \mathbf{F}_o satisfying the Riemann curvature equations, solving the compatibility equations (Riemann curvature equations: $\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{C}_o) = 0$, where $\mathbf{C}_o = \mathbf{F}_o^T \mathbf{F}_o$) hence leading to stress-free configurations are shown in Figure 4 of Section 4.

4 RESULTS

As an application of the concept of morphing by means of an intrinsic deformation, we consider the eversion of a thin cylinder with the procedure described in Section 2, and we contrast it with the eversion of a thick cylinder using the procedure described in Section 3. Starting from a straight cylinder of radius R_0 and height H_0 , we progressively imposed 3D target metric corresponding to cones of higher and higher slanted cone angle α , as described in Section 2. Results from the COMSOL simulation are shown in Figure 3. Starting from the initial cylinder, reported in Fig.3A, the structure deforms into cones (Fig.3B), reaches a flat disk-like configuration (Fig.3C), changes orientation (Fig.3D), and finally reaches a fully-everted cylindrical configuration (Fig.3E).

Figure 2: Eversion of a thin cylinder: (A) Initial straight cylindrical configuration. (B) Intermediate conical configuration, with $\alpha > 0$. (C) Flat configuration ($\alpha = 0$). (D) Intermediate conical configuration with a change of orientation ($\alpha < 0$). (E) Final, fully-everted, straight configuration obtained with $\alpha = -\pi/2$. Colors represent the spontaneous strain amplitude.

A morphing sequence leading to the full eversion of a thick cylinder, obtained by using the concept of exactly compatible active distortions that lead to stress-free configuration since they satisfy the Riemann curvature equations is shown in Figure 4. Further details on the technical aspects on how to compute these configurations can be found in [8]. These methods will be used to infer the mechanisms underlying the everted configurations obtained from observations of the biological templates in WP2.

Figure 4: Eversion of a thick cylinder through the prescription of kinematically compatible active distortion fields. The colors in this figure refer to the initial distance from the axis of the cylinder, showing that the part in red, initially closer to the axis, has been pushed outside while the part in blue, initially more distant, has been brought closer to the axis by the eversion process.

The developed mathematical model is also suited to mirror the macro-scale deformation of smart hydrogels (WP4), in which swelling and contraction are caused by external triggering stimuli such as pH variations. We can plug the resulting changes in the metric of the gel to the developed code, effectively reproducing the behavior of hydrogel layers.

5 BURROWING THROUGH SPATIO-TEMPORAL PATTERNS OF ACTIVE DISTORTIONS

The models using spatio-temporal modulations of active distortions can be used also to investigate quantitatively the burrowing motion of Sipuncula. Building on a model for the

motion of metameric bio-inspired robots within a resistive medium [9], we have developed a 1D model for the locomotion of *Sipuncula* in Agar gels, selected as a medium in which the organism exhibits burrowing behavior in an artificial habitat that enables direct observation, being optically transparent. The basics of the model are reported in Figure 5, where the function $s(X,t)$ can be used to describe a contraction wave traveling along the body (e.g., square or cosine functions), and in Figure 6, where the choice of a large exponent p in the friction law approximates the case $p \rightarrow \infty$ of “free-slip (in the extended regions) and perfect grip (in the contracted ones)”.

Model of a 1D -crawler in resistive media

Figure 5: Kinematics of the 1D model for burrowing motion.

Model of a 1D -crawler in resistive media

Force balance

$$0 = F_f(t) + F_e(t) \quad F_f(t) = \int_{x_1}^{x_2} f(x, t) dx$$

where

$$f(x, t) := -\mu g_p(\epsilon(X, t)) v(x, t)$$

$$\text{where } g_p(\epsilon) := \left(\frac{1}{1 + \epsilon} \right)^p$$

Figure 6: Force balance and friction law for the 1D model for burrowing motion.

The model requires calibration of the resistive force to penetration F_e , see Figure 7. This has been accomplished with indentation tests conducted on Agar gels in custom-designed aquaria, as further detailed in [10].

Calibration of the model for the resistive medium: indentation test results

Figure 7: Calibration of the model for the resistive medium and fitting for the force F_e .

The results of the model are shown in Figure 8 for generic activation patterns (cosine traveling wave of square traveling wave of contraction). The cosine wave pattern proved more accurate to reproduce the results of tracking measurements in observation of *Sipuncula* burrowing motion in aquaria filled with agar gel, see Figure 9. The agar gels had the same composition as the ones used for the force calibration of Figure 7; similarly, the aquaria had the same dimensions.

Model of a 1D -crawler in viscous media: results

$$\dot{x}_1(t) = -\frac{\int_0^L (1 + \epsilon(X, t))^{1-p} \dot{s}(X, t) dX}{\int_0^L (1 + \epsilon(X, t))^{1-p} dX} + \frac{F_e(t)}{\mu \int_0^L (1 + \epsilon(X, t))^{1-p} dX}$$

Figure 8: Prediction of the 1D burrowing model with diverse contraction waves and frictional laws.

The comparison between model predictions and experimental observations shows remarkable accuracy. Further details will be reported in a joint publication [10] involving several members of the Consortium, which is now in preparation.

Model of a 1D -crawler in viscous media: theory vs experiment

Figure 9: Comparison of the predictions of the 1D model with experimental results from observations of the burrowing motion of Sipuncula in agar gel within custom-built aquaria.

CONCLUSIONS

The MAPWORMS project introduces an innovative morphing robot concept inspired by the shape-morphing abilities of marine worms, particularly Sipuncula. The project aims at developing worm-inspired soft robots capable of simple primitive movements through various actuation units. A mathematical and computational model has been developed to link the morphological changes of Sipuncula with the macro-scale behavior of smart actuators and materials by means of the concept of target metric control. A computational model has been developed to solve inverse morphing problems and locomotion problems, namely, how to program shapes and motion patterns by prescribing suitable fields of active distortion that simulate in synthetic systems the muscular actuation driving the biological templates.

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